

7-Methyl-2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde Thiosemicarbazone as Analytical Reagent for Copper,—Cobalt— and Nickel(II)

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Thiosemicarbazones have been frequently employed for spectrophotometric determination of inorganic ions¹. Metal thiosemicarbazone complexes possess various biological activities².

In this paper analytical properties of 7-methyl-2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (7-Me-2-Cl-QAT) and its utility in spectrophotometric determination of cobalt(II), copper(II) and nickel(II).

Results and Discussion

Me-QAT is soluble in dimethyl formamide (DMF) and water, sparingly soluble in alcohol and acetone, and insoluble in chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and cyclohexanone. A $1.862 \times 10^{-8} M$ solution of Me-QAT is stable for a week in 1:1 (v/v) water-DMF mixture, and the cobalt, copper and nickel complexes are stable for 24 h.

The reagent (7Me-2Cl-QAT) in DMF-water (3:2) solution at pH 6, exhibits strong absorption at 350 nm with molar extinction coefficient of $2.746 \times 10^{-3} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The reagent shows shoulder at 390 nm in alkaline medium.

Determination of Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}: In aqueous media, the metal complexes are precipitated but they are soluble in 20% (v/v) DMF-water medium. The reaction is rapid and require no heating for colour development. The characteristics of the metal complexes are summarised in Table 1. Dissociation constants were determined by Job's method³ and mole-ratio method⁴.

Effect of foreign ions: Test solutions of Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} (2 ppm) and buffer solution and a number of representative ions were examined to study their

interference in determination of metal ions. The tolerance limit for cobalt(II) are Ga^{III} and Mo^{VI} 70, Ca^{II} 100; for copper(II) is Mo^{VI} 150; and for nickel(II) are Ce^{III} 100, Al^{III} and Ga^{III} 80, Mo^{VI} and Pt^{VI} 20, Mn^{II} and W^{VI} 10. Tolerance limit for various anions (2% error) in determination of 2 ppm each of Co^{II}, Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} are cyanide (none), acetate (1000), thiocyanate (1000), oxalate (1000), thiourea (1000), citrate (none), phosphate (1000), fluoride (1000), EDTA (none), nitrate (none), acetate (none), tartarate (none).

TABLE 1—PHYSICO-CHEMICAL AND ANALYTICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Characteristics	Co	Cu	Ni
1.	Moles of (7-Me-2-Cl-QAT) required per mole of metal ion	2	1	1
2.	λ_{max} (nm)	410	400	410
3.	Beer's law range (ppm)	5	5	4
4.	Optimum concentration range (ppm) Ringbom plot	1.0-2.5	2.1-4.4	2.8-4.5
5.	Optimum pH	8	4	6
6.	Dissociation constant	5.879×10^{-7}	1.894×10^{-5}	1.238×10^{-6}
7.	Mean absorbance	0.27	0.57	0.275
8.	Molar absorptivity ($\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	1.445×10^3	3.434×10^3	1.67385×10^3
9.	Sandell sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$)	0.22	0.18	0.35

Experimental

7Me-2Cl-QAT was synthesised⁵ by refluxing equimolar amount of 7-methyl-2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde and thiosemicarbazide in minimum

amount of ethanol for 1 h. The product was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 176–77° (Found : C, 50.81 ; H, 4.91 ; N, 20.00%). The spectra were recorded on Carl-Zeiss and Hitachi 330 specol spectrophotometers. An Elico digital pH meter was used.

A stock solution of cobalt(II) (1 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared from cobalt sulphate hexahydrate and standardised⁶. Buffer solutions were prepared and standardised⁶. Buffer solutions were prepared from Na₂B₄O₇ solution (pH 8) from 0.2 M acetic acid + 0.2 M sodium acetate (pH 4 and 5).

Test solutions were prepared with test ions (2.5–5.0 ppm), 1.862 × 10⁻³ M Me-QAT (1.2 ml) and buffer (1.0 ml) and diluted to 10 ml with water-DMF (1 : 1). Spectrum was measured over the region 350–650 nm with the reagent blank as reference.

Samples were prepared with buffer (10 ml ; pH 8 for Co, pH 4 for Cu, and pH 5 for Ni), metal ions (Co 2.5, Cu 5 Ni 2.5 ppm), DMF (2.5 ml), 1.862 × 10⁻³ M Me-QAT (1.0 ml) and diluted to 10 ml with water-DMF (1 : 1). Absorbance was measured at 410 nm for Ni^{II} against reagent blank as reference.

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